

Table S2*Excluded Studies*

Paper	Reason for Exclusion
1 Asici, E., & Sari, H. I. (2021). A proposed model to explain happiness in college students: the roles of perceived parenting styles, emotional self-efficacy, and forgiveness. <i>Journal of Adult Development</i> , 28(4), 332-345. https://doi.org/10.1007/s10804-021-09378-0	The evaluated variables do not align with the objective.
2 Baroudi, S., & Shaya, N. (2022). Exploring predictors of teachers' self-efficacy for online teaching in the Arab world amid COVID-19. <i>Education and Information Technologies</i> , 27(6), 8093-8110. https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-022-10946-4	The sample does not align with the objective.
3 Boncquet, M., Lavrijsen, J., Vansteenkiste, M., Verschueren, K., & Soenens, B. (2022). "You are so smart!": The role of giftedness, parental feedback, and parents' mindsets in predicting students' mindsets. <i>Gifted Child Quarterly</i> , 66(3), 220-237. https://doi.org/10.1177/00169862221084238	The sample does not align with the objective.
4 Butt, Z. & Mushtag, M. (2016). Parental support: A predictor of self-efficacy and academic achievement in college students. <i>International Journal of Research in Education and Psychology</i> , 2(1), 23-31.	The sample does not align with the objective.
5 Buchanan, T., & LeMoyné, T. (2020). Helicopter parenting and the moderating impact of gender and single-parent family structure on self-efficacy and well-being. <i>The Family Journal</i> , 28(3), 262-272. https://doi.org/10.1177/1066480720925829	The sample does not align with the objective.
6 Cheung, C. S. (2019). Parents' involvement and adolescents' school adjustment: Teacher-student relationships as a mechanism of change. <i>School Psychology</i> , 34(4), 350-362. https://doi.org/10.1037/spq0000288	The evaluated variables do not align with the objective.
7 Curelaru, V., Muntele-Hendres, D., Diac, G., & Duca, D. S. (2020). Children's and mothers' achievement goal orientations and self-efficacy: Dyadic contributions to students' well-being. <i>Sustainability</i> , 12(5), 1785. https://doi.org/10.3390/su12051785	The evaluated variables do not align with the objective.
8 Diaconu-Gherasim, L. R., Brumariu, L. E., & Hurley, J. G. (2022). Adolescents' perceptions of contextual factors: Links with intrinsic motivation and academic achievement. <i>Current Psychology</i> , 41, 5578-5593. https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-020-01076-6	Measure outside the academic context.
9 Fairless, M. E., Somers, C. L., Goutman, R. L., Kevern, C. A., Pernice, F. M., & Barnett, D. (2021). Adolescent achievement: Relative contributions of social emotional learning, self-efficacy, and microsystem supports. <i>Education and Urban Society</i> , 53(5), 561-584. https://doi.org/10.1177/0013124520962085	The evaluated variables do not align with the objective.
10 Ferracez Otero, M. J., Lorenzo Moledo, M., Godás Otero, A., & Santos Rego, M. Á. (2021). Students' mediator variables in the relationship between family involvement and academic performance: Effects of the styles of involvement. <i>Psicología Educativa. Revista de los Psicólogos de la Educación</i> , 27(1), 85-92. https://doi.org/10.5093/psed2020a19	The evaluated variables do not align with the objective.
11 Fisher, Y., & Kostelitz, Y. (2015). Teachers' self-efficacy vs. parental involvement: Prediction and implementation. <i>Leadership and Policy in Schools</i> , 14(3), 279-307. https://doi.org/10.1080/15700763.2014.997938	The sample does not align with the objective.
12 Gubbins, V., & Otero, G. (2020). Parental involvement and low-SES children's academic achievement in early elementary school: New evidence from Chile. <i>Educational Studies</i> , 46(5), 548-569. https://doi.org/10.1080/03055698.2019.1620691	The evaluated variables do not align with the objective.
13 Gubbins, V., & Otero, G. (2020). Determinants of parental involvement in primary school: Evidence from Chile. <i>Educational Review</i> , 72(2), 137-156. https://doi.org/10.1080/00131911.2018.1487386	The sample does not align with the objective.

14	Ion, I. E., Lupu, R., & Nicolae, E. (2022). Academic achievement and professional aspirations: between the impacts of family, self-efficacy and school counselling. <i>Journal of Family Studies</i> , 28(2), 587-610. https://doi.org/10.1080/13229400.2020.1746685	The evaluated variables do not align with the objective.
15	Kang, L., Li, C. Chen, D., & Bao, X. (2024). Parental involvement, academic self-efficacy, and depression on academic performance among Chinese students during COVID-19 pandemic. <i>Psychology Research and Behavior Management</i> , 17, 201-216. https://doi.org/10.2147/prbm.s447485	The evaluated variables do not align with the objective.
16	Kaygisiz, S., & Balçikanli, C. (2021). Is it possible to teach english through EBA TV? Exploring student teachers' concerns and self-efficacy beliefs. <i>Journal of Educational Technology and Online Learning</i> , 4(3), 489-502. http://dx.doi.org/10.31681/jetol.932218	The sample does not align with the objective.
17	Kigobe, J., Ghesquière, P., Ng'Umbi, M., & Van Leeuwen, K. (2019). Parental involvement in educational activities in Tanzania: understanding motivational factors. <i>Educational Studies</i> , 45(5), 613-632. https://doi.org/10.1080/03055698.2018.1509780	The sample does not align with the objective.
18	Lerner, R. E., & Grolnick, W. S. (2020). Maternal involvement and children's academic motivation and achievement: The roles of maternal autonomy support and children's affect. <i>Motivation and Emotion</i> , 44(3), 373-388. https://doi.org/10.1007/s11031-019-09813-6	The evaluated variables do not align with the objective.
19	Lerner, R. E., Grolnick, W. S., Caruso, A. J., & Levitt, M. R. (2022). Parental involvement and children's academics: The roles of autonomy support and parents' motivation for involvement. <i>Contemporary Educational Psychology</i> , 68, 1-23. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cedpsych.2021.102039	The evaluated variables do not align with the objective.
20	Li, Y., Hu, T., Ge, T., & Auden, E. (2019). The relationship between home-based parental involvement, parental educational expectation and academic performance of middle school students in mainland China: A mediation analysis of cognitive ability. <i>International Journal of Educational Research</i> , 97, 139-153. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2019.08.003	The evaluated variables do not align with the objective.
21	Liou, P. Y., Wang, C. L., & Lin, J. J. (2019). Pathways of parental involvement through students' motivational beliefs to science achievement. <i>Educational Psychology</i> , 39(7), 960-980. https://doi.org/10.1080/01443410.2019.1617410	The evaluated variables do not align with the objective.
22	Ma, Y., Siu, A., & Tse, W. S. (2018). The role of high parental expectations in adolescents' academic performance and depression in Hong Kong. <i>Journal of Family Issues</i> , 39(9), 2505-2522. https://doi.org/10.1177/0192513X18755194	The evaluated variables do not align with the objective.
23	Mbaluka, S. N., Brand, J. L., & Henry Saturne, B. (2021). Associating student self-discipline and parental involvement in students' academic activities with student academic performance. <i>Journal of Research on Christian Education</i> , 30(3), 270-293. https://doi.org/10.1080/10656219.2021.1994073	The evaluated variables do not align with the objective.
24	Otani, M. (2020). Parental involvement and academic achievement among elementary and middle school students. <i>Asia Pacific Education Review</i> , 21(1), 1-25. https://doi.org/10.1007/s12564-019-09614-z	The evaluated variables do not align with the objective.
25	Paulson, A., Kulinna, P. H., & van der Mars, H. (2022). Effect of parental involvement on perceptions of physical education. <i>Physical Educator</i> , 79(4), 441-465. https://doi.org/10.18666/TPE-2022-V79-I4-11265	Article restricted to a specific curricular area
26	Peng, S. L. (2021). The Power of Feedback Manipulations: Effects on Taiwanese Junior High School Students' Expectancy-Value Beliefs and Academic Performance. <i>Bulletin of Educational Psychology</i> , 53(2), 383-406. https://doi.org/10.6251/BEP.202112_53(2).0006	The sample does not align with the objective.
27	Philippe, K., Chabanet, C., Issanchou, S., Grønhøj, A., Aschemann-Witzel, J., & Monnery-Patris, S. (2022). Parental feeding practices and parental involvement in child feeding in Denmark: gender differences and predictors. <i>Appetite</i> , 170, 105876. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appet.2021.105876	The evaluated variables do not align with the objective.

28	Santos Rego, M. A., Ferraces Otero, M. J., Godás Otero, A., & Lorenzo Moledo, M. D. M. (2018). Do cooperative learning and family involvement improve variables linked to academic performance? <i>Psicothema</i> , 30(2), 212-217. https://doi.org/10.7334/psicothema2017.311	The evaluated variables do not align with the objective.
29	Silinskas, G. & Kikas, E. (2019). Parental Involvement in Math Homework: Links to Children's Performance and Motivation. <i>Scandinavian Journal of Educational Research</i> , 63(1), 17-37. https://doi.org/10.1080/00313831.2017.1324901	The evaluated variables do not align with the objective.
30	Singh, K., & Gera, B. (2016). Achievement anxiety among senior secondary school students in relation to emotional self-efficacy and parental involvement. <i>Man In India</i> , 96(5), 1341-1348.	The evaluated variables do not align with the objective.
31	Suh, H. N., & Flores, L. Y. (2017). Relative deprivation and career decision self-efficacy: Influences of self-regulation and parental educational attainment. <i>The Career Development Quarterly</i> , 65(2), 145-158. https://doi.org/10.1002/cdq.12088	The sample does not align with the objective.
32	Thomas, V., Muls, J., De Backer, F., & Lombaerts, K. (2020). Middle school student and parent perceptions of parental involvement: Unravelling the associations with school achievement and wellbeing. <i>Educational Studies</i> , 46(4), 404-421. https://doi.org/10.1080/03055698.2019.1590182	The evaluated variables do not align with the objective.
33	Van Vo, D., & Csapó, B. (2022). Exploring students' science motivation across grade levels and the role of inductive reasoning in science motivation. <i>European Journal of Psychology of Education</i> , 37(3), 807-829. https://doi.org/10.1007/s10212-021-00568-8	The evaluated variables do not align with the objective.
34	Wang, G., Zhang, S., & Cai, J. (2021). How are parental expectations related to students' beliefs and their perceived achievement? <i>Educational Studies in Mathematics</i> , 108(3), 429-450. https://doi.org/10.1007/s10649-021-10073-w	The evaluated variables do not align with the objective.
35	Wehrspann, E., Dotterer, A. M., & Lowe, K. (2016). The nature of parental involvement in middle school: Examining nonlinear associations. <i>Contemporary School Psychology</i> , 20(3), 193-204. https://doi.org/10.1007/s40688-015-0071-9	The evaluated variables do not align with the objective.
36	Wei, J., Pomerantz, E. M.; Ng, F. F. Y.; Yu, Y. H.; Wang, M. Z., & Wang, Q. (2022). Do the effects of parents' involvement in youth's academic adjustment vary with youth's developmental phase? A longitudinal investigation in China. <i>Contemporary Educational Psychology</i> , 71(102118). https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cedpsych.2022.102118	The evaluated variables do not align with the objective.
37	Williams, K., Swift, J., Williams, H., & Van Daal, V. (2017). Raising children's self-efficacy through parental involvement in homework. <i>Educational Research</i> , 59(3), 316-334. https://doi.org/10.1080/00131881.2017.1344558	Qualitative Data
38	Wu, J., Barger, M. M., Oh, D., & Pomerantz, E. M. (2022). Parents' daily involvement in children's math homework and activities during early elementary school. <i>Child Development</i> , 93(5), 1347-1364. https://doi.org/10.1111/cdev.13774	The sample does not align with the objective.
39	Yildirim, S. (2019). Predicting mathematics achievement: The role of socioeconomic status, parental involvement, and self-confidence. <i>Education and Science</i> , 44(198), 99-113. https://doi.org/10.15390/EB.2019.7868	The sample does not align with the objective.
40	Yomtov, D., Plunkett, S. W., Sands, T., & Reid, A. (2015). Parenting and ninth graders' self-efficacy and relational self-esteem in Latino immigrant families. <i>Family and Consumer Sciences Research Journal</i> , 43(3), 269-283. https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1111/fcsr.12102	The sample does not align with the objective.
